

Workshop "THE ELECTRIC DECADE"

17 January 2024 | 8.45 – 12.00 CET | venue: online

Discover how electrification
technologies support the EU's climate
goals

[More info & registration ...](#)

Funded by
the European Union

Agenda highlights

- Discussion on challenges and innovative catalytic reactor solutions for the process industry
- Participating Horizon Europe Projects: e-CODUCT, EReTech, eQATOR, TITAN and STORMING

Program

Speakers

Ready to be part of the transformation?

Engage in discussions with experts from leading projects

Register Now

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